

SUPPRESSION OF NARROW FREQUENCY BANDS IN MULTICARRIER TRANSMISSION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

A method to enhance capacity in *Discrete Multitone Transmission* (DMT) systems is presented. This paper addresses the problem, how to reduce the transmit *power spectral density* (PSD) of the DMT signal in specific narrow frequency bands below a certain level. One example is VDSL signaling [1, 2] in the presence of amateur radio. Only a small amount of egress is allowed inside these very narrow frequency bands. If a DMT system operates in such a situation, in the conventional system all tones inside these frequency bands and a lot of adjacent tones must be loaded with zeros to meet the requirements on the egress. In our proposal we devote some unused tones to reduce the PSD inside these frequency bands. With this method the number of idle tones can be reduced substantially. To demonstrate the increase of the number of usable tones, we will show a realistic example in the context of VDSL.

1 INTRODUCTION

A lot of currently used transmission systems multiplex data in frequency-domain rather than in time-domain [3]. This method is commonly known as DMT and *Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplex* (OFDM) [4, 5].

In these systems the frequency band is splitted up into a large number of small subchannels. Subchannels are considered as independent from each other with their own modulation formats. In the transmitter, the *Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform* (IDFT) is used to spread the data over the given frequency band. The *Discrete Fourier Transform* (DFT) in the receiver reverts this process [6, 7].

IDFT and DFT perform filtering with a prototype filter with rectangular impulse response and modulated versions of this impulse response [8]. Due to the high sidelobes of the prototype filter in frequency domain, only a poor spectral containment is achieved. In case, that the PSD should be reduced below a certain level inside several frequency bands, all tones inside these frequency bands and a large number of adjacent tones must be loaded with zeros. In the remaining text we use the term HAM bands to refer to these frequency bands.

In this paper we propose a compensation method which uses some unused tones to reduce the spread out of neighbor

channels into the HAM bands. The principle of this method is described in detail in Section 2 and 3. Simulation results in the context of VDSL are presented in Section 4.

2 THE COMPENSATION METHOD

In a DMT transmitter modulation is done by an IDFT block. We denote the data to be transmitted at block l by $X_{l,k}$. Index k specifies the tone and must be in the range $k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$, where N denotes the number of subchannels. The N data $X_{l,k}$ are extended by their conjugate complex values and applied to the IDFT of blocklength $2N$. Due to the conjugate complex extension a real-valued DMT symbol $x_l[n], n = 0, 1, \dots, 2N - 1$, is obtained. To allow a simple frequency-domain equalization in the receiver, a Cyclic Prefix [9] is added to each data block. Figure 1 shows the block diagram of this transmitter. The transmit filter of tone k is characterized by the impulse-response

$$h_k[n] = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2N} e^{j\frac{\pi}{N}k(n-P)}, & n = 0, 1, \dots, 2N + P - 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The transfer function $H_k(e^{j\theta})$ of $h_k[n]$ is centered around the normalized frequency $\theta = k\frac{\pi}{N}$. If the PSD of the sequence $x[n]$ has to be reduced below a certain level inside the frequency range $(k-1)\frac{\pi}{N} \leq \theta < (k+1)\frac{\pi}{N}$, it is not sufficient to idle this tone. Due to the sidelobes of the transmit filters of the neighboring tones, a lot of adjacent channels must be nulled, too. These channels are lost for information transmission leading to a decrease of spectral efficiency.

Our compensation method allows to reduce the number of idle tones outside the HAM bands. Some of these idle tones outside and inside the HAM bands are used to transmit compensating signals. The compensating signals should

Figure 1: Block diagram of the DMT transmitter.

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approximate the interference of the neighboring tones inside the HAM bands and cancel it out.

If we assume for the moment, that only one tone u is used to transmit the sequence $X_{l,u}$ and all other tones are idle, the output of the DMT modulator can be written as

$$x[n] = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} X_{l,u} h_u[n - lM] + \text{CC}, \quad (2)$$

where $M = 2N + P$ is the duration of one DMT symbol plus Cyclic Prefix. The term CC denotes the conjugate complex of the first term in (2).

We denote the set, which contains the indices of the idle tones used by our compensation method as $\mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{I}}$. Then the time-domain signal of the modified DMT modulator can be written as

$$x[n] = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} (X_{l,u} h_u[n - lM] + \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} X_{l-r,u} ([\mathbf{c}_u[r]]_1 h_{i_1}[n - lM] + \dots + [\mathbf{c}_u[r]]_I h_{i_I}[n - lM])) + \text{CC}. \quad (3)$$

The first row corresponds to an ordinary DMT signal, when only $X_{l,u}$ is applied to tone u . The remaining rows correspond to the transmission of compensating signals on tones $i_l \in \mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{I}}$, $l = 1, 2, \dots, I$. The number I is the cardinality of set $\mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{I}}$. For $r = 0$, the compensating signal to be transmitted on tone i is the current data $X_{l,u}$ scaled by $[\mathbf{c}_u[0]]_i$, the i -th element of the I -element vector $\mathbf{c}_u[0]$. For $r \neq 0$, the compensating signals are derived from already sent data $X_{l-r,u}$, $r = 1, 2, \dots, R - 1$. The number R determines the memory. The optimal choice of the weighting vectors $\mathbf{c}_u[r]$, $r = 0, 1, \dots, R - 1$, will be discussed in Section 3.

Using vectors, equation (3) can be written as

$$x[n] = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} (X_{l,u} h_u[n - lM] + \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} X_{l-r,u} \mathbf{c}_u^T[r] \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}[n - lM]) + \text{CC}, \quad (4)$$

where the vector $\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}[n]$ contains the impulse responses of the transmit filters used to transmit the compensating signals. It can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}[n] = [h_{i_1}[n], h_{i_2}[n], \dots, h_{i_I}[n]]^T \quad (5)$$

with $\{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_I\} = \mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{I}}$.

When not only tone u is used for information transmission, but all tones $u \in \mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{U}}$, the output of the DMT modulator is

$$x[n] = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} (\mathbf{X}_l^T \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{U}}[n - lM] + \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} \mathbf{X}_{l-r}^T C[r] \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}[n - lM]) + \text{CC}. \quad (6)$$

The set $\mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{U}}$ consists of the indices of the tones used for transmission of information. The vectors $\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{U}}[n]$ and $\mathbf{X}_l$ contain the impulse responses of the filters used for information

transmission and the data to be transmitted, respectively. They can be written as

$$\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{U}}[n] = [h_{u_1}[n], h_{u_2}[n], \dots, h_{u_U}[n]]^T \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mathbf{X}_l = [X_{l,u_1}, X_{l,u_2}, \dots, X_{l,u_U}]^T, \quad (8)$$

with $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_U\} = \mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{U}}$. U is the number of elements in set $\mathcal{K}_{\mathcal{U}}$. The element (m, n) of the $U \times I$ weighting matrix $C[r]$ describes, which portion of the data X_{l-r,u_m} should be transmitted on tone i_n at time l . With the vectors $\mathbf{c}_u[r]$ introduced in equation (3), we can write

$$C[r] = [\mathbf{c}_{u_1}[r], \mathbf{c}_{u_2}[r], \dots, \mathbf{c}_{u_U}[r]]^T. \quad (9)$$

3 CALCULATION OF THE WEIGHTING MATRICES

We choose the matrices $C[r]$ to minimize the integral of the PSD $S_{xx}(e^{j\theta})$ inside the HAM bands. To get the PSD $S_{xx}(e^{j\theta})$, first we calculate the *autocorrelation function* (ACF) $R_{xx}[m]$ of $x[n]$ and then apply the Fourier Transform to it. Because $x[n]$ is a cyclostationary process, we have to calculate first the time dependent ACF $R_{xx}[n, m] = E[x^*[n]x[n + m]]$ at time n and lag m and take the average over n . After some algebraic manipulations we obtain

$$R_{xx}[m] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} (\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{U}}^H[n] P \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{U}}[n + m] + \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} (\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}^H[n] C^H[r] P \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{U}}[n + m + rM] + \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{U}}^H[n] P C[r] \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}[n + m - rM]) + \sum_{\rho=0}^{R-1} \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}^H[n] C^H[r] P C[\rho] \mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{I}}[n + m + (r - \rho)M])) + \text{CC}. \quad (10)$$

The $U \times U$ diagonal matrix P contains the power of the data to be transmitted,

$$P = \text{diag}\{\sigma_{u_1}^2, \sigma_{u_2}^2, \dots, \sigma_{u_U}^2\}, \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma_u^2 = E\{|X_{l,u}|^2\}$. To obtain equation (10), we have assumed stationary data sequences on each tone. Furthermore, the data must be statistically independent.

The Fourier Transform applied to (10) yields the PSD

$$S_{xx}(e^{j\theta}) = \sum_{m=-RM+1}^{m=RM-1} R_{xx}[m] e^{-j\theta m}. \quad (12)$$

Because the ACF $R_{xx}[m]$ has only a support in the range $-RM < m < RM$, the summation in (12) extends only on a finite interval. If we set $C[r] = 0$ in equation (10) and evaluate (12), we obtain the PSD of an ordinary DMT signal.

With equation (12) we are now able to formulate the cost function

$$J(C[0], C[1], \dots, C[R-1]) = \int_0^{2\pi} W(e^{j\theta}) S_{xx}(e^{j\theta}) d\theta, \quad (13)$$

which we want to minimize with respect to the matrices $C[r]$. $W(e^{j\theta})$ is a weighting function. If we set $W(e^{j\theta})$ equal to one inside the HAM bands and equal to zero elsewhere, equation (13) delivers the transmitted power inside the HAM bands. This choice of the weighting function minimizes the power transmitted in the HAM bands. However, this is not exactly that what we are interested in. The exact goal is to minimize the maximal value of $S_{xx}(e^{j\theta})$ inside the HAM bands. Of course, we can formulate a min max criterion to obtain this goal, but this criterion is mathematically more tricky to handle. Instead, we do not use a rectangular window function $W(e^{j\theta})$, but a smooth weighting function: The transitions from one to zero and vice versa are done by linear slopes. This choice corresponds neither to the min max solution nor to the minimal transmitted power inside the HAM bands, but simulations have shown, that this choice delivers better results than minimizing the transmitted power inside certain frequency bands.

The cost function (13) is a quadratic function in the matrices $C[r]$ and has therefore a unique minimum. This minimum is described by the set of equations

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial [C[r]]_{u,i}} J(C[0], C[1], \dots, C[R-1]) = 0 \quad (14)$$

with $r = 0, 1, \dots, R-1$, $u = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_U$, and $i = i_1, i_2, \dots, i_I$. $[C[r]]_{u,i}$ refers to element (u, i) in matrix $C[r]$.

This set of equations can be solved by U independent linear equation systems. Each value of u corresponds to one linear equation system with RI unknown variables. The equation system belonging to a fixed value $u_x \in \mathcal{K}_U$ describes the coefficients contained in the x -th row of all R matrices $C[r]$. If we denote the x -th row of matrix $C[r]$ by $\mathbf{c}_{u_x}^T[r]$ (compare with (9)), the vector of unknown variables corresponding to u_x can be written as $\mathbf{f}_{u_x} = [\mathbf{c}_{u_x}^T[0], \mathbf{c}_{u_x}^T[1], \dots, \mathbf{c}_{u_x}^T[R-1]]^T$.

At time l , the data X_{l-r, u_x} multiplied by the elements of the vector $\mathbf{c}_{u_x}[r]$ must be applied to all tones $i \in \mathcal{K}_I$ to compensate for the data X_{l-r, u_x} . The coefficients contained in row y , $y \neq x$, of all matrices $C[r]$ are used to compensate for tone u_y . The statistical independence of data we have assumed during the derivation of $S_{xx}(e^{j\theta})$ implies that the data transmitted by one tone contain no information concerning data delivered by other tones. Minimizing the effect of data carried by one tone is hence done by considering only this specific tone and no others, the equations described by (14) split up into as many systems as tones are contained in set $\mathcal{K}_U$.

The coefficient matrices of all U equation systems are the same and can be written as a block matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} A_{0,0} & A_{0,1} & \dots & A_{0,R-1} \\ A_{1,0} & A_{1,1} & \dots & A_{1,R-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{R-1,0} & A_{R-1,1} & \dots & A_{R-1,R-1} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

where the sub matrices of this matrix are defined as

$$A_{k,l} = \int_0^{2\pi} W(e^{j\theta}) H_{\mathcal{I}}^*(e^{j\theta}) H_{\mathcal{I}}^T(e^{j\theta}) e^{-j\theta(l-k)M} d\theta. \quad (16)$$

The vector $\mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{I}}(e^{j\theta})$ contains the Fourier Transforms $H_i(e^{j\theta})$ of the filters $h_i[n]$ used to transmit compensating signals and can be written as

$$\mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{I}}(e^{j\theta}) = [H_{i_1}(e^{j\theta}), H_{i_2}(e^{j\theta}), \dots, H_{i_I}(e^{j\theta})]^T. \quad (17)$$

The right hand side of the equation system corresponding to $u = u_x$ is the block vector

$$\mathbf{d}_{u_x} = [\mathbf{d}_{u_x}^T[0], \mathbf{d}_{u_x}^T[1], \dots, \mathbf{d}_{u_x}^T[R-1]]^T \quad (18)$$

with the sub vectors

$$\mathbf{d}_{u_x}[r] = - \int_0^{2\pi} W(e^{j\theta}) H_{u_x}(e^{j\theta}) \mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{I}}^*(e^{j\theta}) e^{j\theta r M} d\theta. \quad (19)$$

$H_{u_x}(e^{j\theta})$ is the Fourier Transform of the transmit filter $h_{u_x}[n]$.

With (15) and (18) the equations for $u = u_x$ read

$$A \mathbf{f}_{u_x} = \mathbf{d}_{u_x}, \quad (20)$$

which can be solved for $\mathbf{f}_{u_x}$. All U values $u_x \in \mathcal{K}_U$ deliver the complete set of coefficients $C[r]$.

4 RESULTS

In this section we present an example in the context of VDSL. One key problem in VDSL is the existence of extremely narrow frequency bands occupied by amateur radio. The two lowest HAM bands are located at 1.81 – 2.00 MHz and 3.50 – 3.80 MHz [1]. Inside these bands the transmitted PSD must be reduced by an amount of 20 dB. To meet these requirements on the PSD inside these frequency bands, it is not sufficient to null subchannels overlapping with HAM bands. Additionally, a lot of adjacent channels have to be loaded with zeros to achieve the required reduction of the PSD. In the following examples we show now the potential of our compensation method to reduce the number of idle subchannels.

The number of tones in all systems presented is equal to 1024. The length of the applied Cyclic Prefix is equal to 64. The bandwidth of one subchannel is equal to 4.3125 kHz.

The first simulation performs on a system, which uses no special techniques to suppress the PSD inside the HAM bands. The necessary suppression is achieved only by nulling of tones near the HAM bands. This system is denoted as System A.

System B applies the proposed spectral compensation method. The parameter R of the compensation method has been chosen equal to 2. In the derivation of the compensation method we have assumed, that all tones $i \in \mathcal{K}_I$ are used to compensate for the influence of all tones $u \in \mathcal{K}_U$. However, only tones close enough to a tone u , $u \in \mathcal{K}_U$, will have noticeable effect in compensation of the contribution of tone u . Therefore, not all tones $u \in \mathcal{K}_U$ share all compensation tones $i \in \mathcal{K}_I$. With the same argument, tones far inside the HAM bands need not to be used for compensation. Tones inside the HAM bands, which are not used by the compensation method, must be loaded with zeros. The first row in table 1 shows some parameters of System B. Column one and two list, for the first and second HAM band, respectively, the tones, the influence of which must be compensated. The last two columns list the compensation tones. The two lines in each row correspond to the lower and upper edges of the HAM bands, respectively.

System C again refers to the spectral compensation method. The parameter R of the compensation method now has been set equal to 1. Table 1 lists some parameters of system C.

	K_U		K_I	
	1st HAM	2nd HAM	1st HAM	2nd HAM
System B	411-417	803-809	418-422	810-814
	466-472	884-870	461-465	879-883
System C	410-416	802-808	417-421	809-813
	467-473	885-871	462-466	880-884

Table 1: Tones, the influence of which should be compensated and idle tones used for compensation, respectively. The first line within one row addresses the lower edges of the HAM bands, whereas the second line corresponds to the upper edges of the HAM bands.

	lost tones	operations
System A	413-471, 805-888	
System B	418-465, 810-883	560
System C	417-466, 809-884	280

Table 2: Lost tones and the additional complex operations required by the compensation method. System B gains 21 tones compared to System A, System C gains 17 tones compared to System A.

Table 2 lists the tones, which cannot be used to transmit information, for all three systems. System B, using the proposed method, loses only 2 tones on each edge of the HAM bands, whereas System A loses 5 or 6 tones per edge. System B can use 21 tones more for information transmission than System A. The last column in table 2 lists the number of additional complex operations per DMT symbol to gain this improvement.

Figure 2 shows the PSDs of the transmitted signals of system A and system B. Due to the compensation pulses, the PSD of system B decreases steeper at the edges of the HAM bands than the PSD of system A.

Figure 2: Achieved PSDs of system A (dashed) and system B (solid). The PSDs are only shown around a) the first and b) the second HAM band. The gray shaded areas correspond to the HAM bands.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed a modified DMT transmitter, which increases the spectral efficiency in environments, where the permitted PSD mask contains some narrow frequency bands, where the allowed PSD must be reduced below a certain level. We demonstrated the proposed method by an example

in the context of VDSL, where the PSD of the transmitted signal must be reduced inside certain frequency bands which are occupied by amateur radio.

References

- [1] “Transmission and Multiplexing (tm); Access transmission on metallic access cables; Very high speed Digital Subscriber Line; Part 1: Functional requirements”, Draft Technical Specification TS 101 270-1 V1.1.6, ETSI, Aug. 1999.
- [2] T. Starr, J. M. Cioffi, and P. J. Silverman, *Understanding Digital Subscriber Line Technology*, Communications Engineering and Emerging Technologies Series. Prentice Hall, 1999.
- [3] B. R. Saltzberg, “Performance of an Efficient Parallel Data Transmission System”, *IEEE Transactions on Communications Technology*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 805–811, Dec. 1967.
- [4] J. A. C. Bingham, “Multicarrier Modulation for Data Transmission: An Idea Whose Time Has Come”, *ComMag*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 5–14, May 1990.
- [5] I. Kalet, “The Multitone Channel”, *COM*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 119–124, Feb. 1989.
- [6] B. Hirosaki, “An Orthogonally Multiplexed QAM System Using the Discrete Fourier Transform”, *COM*, vol. 29, no. 7, pp. 982–989, July 1981.
- [7] S. B. Weinstein and P. M. Ebert, “Data Transmission by Frequency-Division Multiplexing Using the Discrete Fourier Transform”, *IEEE Transactions on Communications Technology*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 628–634, Oct. 1971.
- [8] P.P. Vaidyanathan, *Multirate Systems and Filter Banks*, Series in Signal Processing. Prentice Hall, 1993.
- [9] A. Peled and A. Ruiz, “Frequency Domain Data Transmission Using Reduced Computational Complexity Algorithm”, in *Proc. IEEE ICASSP*, Denver, CO, 1980, pp. 964–967.